

Table 5. STEAM achievements and environmental ethics gains across course areas in the Turkish middle school curriculum.

Course Area	STEAM Achievements	Environmental Ethics Gains	Source
Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of scientific method and problem solving skills. - Addressing issues such as environmental pollution, climate change and conservation of natural resources on scientific basis. - Efficient use of energy resources and the introduction of renewable energy technologies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raising awareness about global problems such as environmental pollution and climate change. - Protection of natural resources and development of sustainability awareness. - Promoting environmentally friendly behaviour. 	<p>Science Course Curriculum (Elementary and Middle School Grades 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8) (Turkish Ministry of National Education, 2018)</p>
Maths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To gain mathematical modelling and data analysis skills. - Analysing and interpreting environmental data (e.g. carbon emissions, energy consumption). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using mathematical thinking skills in solving environmental problems. - Making mathematical calculations for sustainable management of natural resources. 	<p>Science Course Curriculum (Elementary and Middle School Grades 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8) (Turkish Ministry of National Education, 2018)</p> <p>Mathematics Course Teaching Programme (Ministry of National Education of the Republic of Turkey, 2018)</p>
Technology and Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Environmentally friendly use of technological tools and development of recycling projects. - Application of engineering design processes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developing environmentally sensitive designs. - Evaluation of the effects of technological developments on the environment. 	<p>Science Course Curriculum (Elementary and Middle School Grades 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8) (Turkish Ministry of National Education, 2018)</p>

- Introduction of environmentally friendly technologies and integration of these technologies into daily life.

Visual Arts	- Designing art projects from recycled materials. - Encouraging creativity with environment-themed artworks.	- Carrying out artistic works that increase environmental awareness. - Development of visual projects that encourage respect for nature.	Law on Amendments to the Primary Education and Education Law and Certain Other Laws (Government of Turkey, 2012)
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Information Technologies and Software	- Development of algorithmic thinking and coding skills. - Producing digital solutions for environmental problems. - Environmentally friendly use of technological tools.	- Developing digital projects for environmental problems. - Promoting environmentally friendly software and technologies.	Law on Amendments to the Primary Education and Education Law and Certain Other Laws (Government of Turkey, 2012) Turkey's education vision 2023 (Government of Turkey, 2019)
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